

COMPETENCE AMONG TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION TEACHERS IN RELATION TO STUDENT ATTITUDE TOWARDS LEARNING THE SUBJECT

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 7

Pages: 782-796

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2505

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13941112

Manuscript Accepted: 01-10-2024

Competence among Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in Relation to Student Attitude towards Learning the Subject

Raphy V. Abang*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Teaching, indeed, is not merely teaching the students the right virtue but teaching for their development both in the academic and behavior for the betterment of humanity. In fact, this becomes a great concern of technology lectures on how to change the students' negative attitudes in learning Technology and Livelihood Education (Jacobus, 2010). Thus, the focal point of this study was to determine the significant influence of competence among Technology and Livelihood teachers on the student attitude towards learning of 320 junior high school students in selected secondary schools in Kidapawan City, SY 2016-2017. Furthermore, this study made use of the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive correlational technique. Results revealed that the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers had a high level of competence and the respondents claimed that they have positive attitude towards learning the subject. This study further disclosed that competence among TLE teachers was positively correlated with student attitude towards learning. The result implied that the more competent the teachers are, the more positive will be the students' attitude towards learning. School and society relationships were found to be the best predictor of student attitude towards learning.

Keywords: *education, teaching competence, student attitude*

Introduction

Teaching, indeed, is not merely teaching the students the right virtue but teaching for their development both in the academic and behavior for the betterment of humanity. In fact, this becomes a great concern of technology lectures on how to change the students' negative attitudes in learning Technology and Livelihood Education (Jacobus, 2010). In a study conducted in New York City, students fail to achieve better grades in the class due to lack of confidence, knowledge, training and expertise of teachers. The findings revealed that inadequate resources, lack of rooms and poor facilities to be used led to poor interest of students during actual class, which resulted to students' boredom and low performance (Morgan & Hansen, 2008). As a result, students attitude affect their performance through frequent absences, cutting classes and sometimes resulting to lack of motivation, lack of interest to achieve greater grades in their subject and ultimately become hindrance to their success (Laguador, 2013a; Gutierrez, 2012).

In the Philippines, teachers are considered facilitators and motivators of learning. In this manner, teachers must have to be competent enough. Reviews of research have demonstrated that achieving teaching competence in reality are very challenging, where teachers introduce varied strategies, methods into their classroom practice (Alvarez & Espasa, 2009; Downes, 2010). In addition, research has indicated that students are lazy to comply with their task when the activity is a one class fits all, but if students are provided with various activities and wider opportunities to enhance their competence, students develop a better attitude towards studies to really understand the value of being responsible and mature individual (Laguador, 2014).

Technological literacy correlates with the attitude towards technology; therefore, when measuring technological literacy as an outcome of education, one should take the attitude towards technology into account (Ardies, de Maeyer and Gijbels, 2013). In the Philippines secondary school students' interest and attitude towards technology and livelihood education (TLE) as a subject is low. Students have no interest in the subject and their attitude associated with TLE subject appear to affect enrolment and TLE as subject and its impact performance in the subject. These findings revealed that teachers are contributors of the said failure of the students since the teachers are not successful in giving or using all the methods and strategies to bring out students positive attitude toward learning. When students are supported, they are motivated to bring out the best in them. Any sets of activities initiated by the teachers, students in turn become supportive in their class, as up show interest, positive attitude, and active participation (Demir, Desmet, and Hekkert, 2009; Hagger and McIntyre, 2006).

It is in this context that the researcher is eager to determine whether the teaching competence of Technology and Livelihood Education influence the attitude of students towards learning the subject and to possibly conceptualize various methods and strategies to improve the teaching learning process. Thus, the researcher find the need to conduct this study.

Research Objectives

This study was conducted to determine which domain of competence among Technology and Livelihood Education teachers best influences student attitude towards learning the subject. Specifically, it was intended to attain the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of competence among TLE teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. personal and professional values – professional development;
 - 1.2. knowing the student;

- 1.3. learning and teaching process;
- 1.4. monitoring and evaluation of learning and development;
- 1.5. school and society relationships; and
- 1.6. knowledge of curriculum and content.
2. To ascertain the level of student attitude towards learning the subject in terms of:
 - 2.1. general interest in technology;
 - 2.2. attitude towards technology;
 - 2.3. technology as an activity for boys and girls;
 - 2.4. consequences of technology; and
 - 2.5. technology is difficult.
3. To determine the significant relationship between competence among Technology and Livelihood Education teachers and student attitude toward learning the subject.
4. To determine which domain of competence among TLE teachers best influences student attitude towards learning the subject.

Literature Review

Teacher Competence

Teacher effectiveness is a relationship between teachers, pupils and other persons concerned with the educational undertaking. Teaching competency is a combination of traditional ideas that were propounded by great educators in the past on one hand and at the new ideas like-systematic approach to education on the other hand (Rana, 2013). Reviews of research have demonstrated that achieving teaching competence in reality are very challenging, where teachers introduce varied strategies, methods into their classroom practice (Alvarez & Espasa, 2009; Downes, 2010). In addition, research has indicated that students are lazy to comply with their task when the activity is a one class fits all, but if students are provided with various activities to enhance their competence, students develop a better attitude towards studies to really understand the value of being responsible and mature individual (Laguador, 2014).

The quality of education in Serbia is observed through two different approaches to education quality evaluation: the economic approach is directed towards quantitatively measurable goals and outputs of education; humanistic-progressive approach, however, emphasizes the process itself in education. For both approaches to education quality evaluation, teachers' competences represent the key factor. There are some innovations in the concept of teachers' education when it comes to comprehension of the standards for professional competence of the teachers. A teacher's ability to be a reflexive practitioner is, at the same time, both a competence and a tool to advance all other competencies of a teacher (Marinković, Bjekić and Zlatić, 2012).

Teaching competency includes teaching behavior and teaching skills. Teaching behaviors can be linked with knowledge of the subject matter and its presentation. The teacher acquires that knowledge through his continuous efforts and learns presentation during his/her training which determines his effectiveness (Rana, 2013). This is supported by Hamilton-Ekeke (2013), who said that teaching competency is the ability of a teacher manifested through a set of classroom behaviors which is a resultant of the interaction between the presage and the product variables of teaching with in a social setting.

Professional development means the teacher makes efforts to attain high level of student learning and development by taking into account social and cultural differences of students, their background and interests (Ankara, 2006). Professional development refers to many types of educational experiences related to an individual's work. Doctors, lawyers, educators, accountants, engineers, and people in a wide variety of professions and businesses participate in professional development to learn and apply new knowledge and skills that will improve their performance on the job (Mizell, 2010).

Professional development generally refers to ongoing learning opportunities available to teachers and other education personnel through their schools and districts. Effective professional development is often seen as vital to school success and teacher satisfaction, but it has also been criticized for its cost, often vaguely determined goals, and for the lack of data on resulting teacher and school improvement that characterizes many efforts (Editorial Projects in Education Research Center, 2011).

Parsing the strengths and weaknesses of the vast array of programs that purport to invest in teachers' knowledge and skills continues to be a challenge. Today, professional development activities include formal teacher induction, the credits or degrees teachers earn as part of recertification or to receive salary boosts, the national-board-certification process, and participation in subject-matter associations or informal networks (Sawchuk, 2010).

Effective professional development enables educators to develop the knowledge and skills they need to address students' learning challenges. To be effective, professional development requires thoughtful planning followed by careful implementation with feedback to ensure it responds to educators' learning needs (Mizell, 2010). In addition, the goal of professional development is to ensure that teachers have chances to improve their skill and become a better teacher, thus the school must initiate and monitor whether students learn better as a result of it (Sawchuk, 2011; UNESCO, 2014). The professional development of teachers is a change of the whole concept of the teaching profession: how to prepare a teacher, what does his/her job look like, what is his/her role in the educational process, which is directly linked to a whole range of other aspects of the educational process and inevitably causes numerous other

changes, from macro to microsystems (Marinković, 2010).

On the other hand, some researches are contemplating the possibility of adjusting the needs of educational context, teachers and society with the content of the program for professional internship, they are searching for a concept of professional development which will put teachers in the role of active participants of the process of creation, realization, monitoring and evaluation of the program for personal and professional development (Kamenarac, 2011). A positive attitude towards profession can bring the desired quality in education sector by developing sense of duty, professional competence and by giving them an insight of student's needs and problems (Bhargava and Pathy, 2014).

Knowing the students means that the teacher knows all the characteristics, interests and needs of the student, understands the socio-cultural and economic background of the student and his/her parents (Ankara, 2006). It is easy to dismiss the importance of knowing your students as either a vacuous platitude or a statement of the obvious. However, the process of coming to know students as learners is often difficult and challenging, particularly if the students are struggling with schoolwork (Powell and Powell, 2011).

All children have unique learning styles. Students gain strong benefits when their teachers and learning coaches recognize their strengths and weaknesses as learners (Ostwald-Kowald, 2014). Therefore, teachers need to know their students well and be able to adapt their teaching styles to a particular classroom and to individual students (Khatoon, Azeem and Akhtar, 2011). Meanwhile, a good teacher needs to concentrate on his students at their current development stages so that he could teach them well according to their learning interests and needs (Khatoon et al., 2011).

Teaching and learning refers to how the teacher plans, implements and manages the teaching and learning processes (Ankara, 2006). Teaching and learning are about collaboration, working together. It is about the personal growth of teachers of all ages and experiences. It requires courage to be confronted with, share and receive criticism. Teaching is learning and accepting that we cannot succeed all the time. When you start using a new strategy or a new way of relating to your students, it is important to create a safe environment for this experimentation (UNESCO, 2014).

Teaching and learning are important components of education. Therefore, a teacher needs to have his own philosophy of education to help his students and to make himself effective in teaching (Khatoon et al., 2011). To be successful in teaching and learning, a teacher must have ability and skill in teaching and instilling discipline to his students (Kheruniah, 2013). Another study claimed that motivation is an important area of teaching and learning process in the classroom in which it adversely affects teaching performance of secondary school teachers (Khatoon et al., 2011).

Monitoring and evaluation of learning and development signifies that the teacher evaluates development and achievement of students with regard to learning (Ankara, 2006). Morin (2014) stated that self-monitoring is a skill used to keep track of your own actions and performance. On the other hand, plans and design instructions are based on content area of knowledge, diverse student characteristics, student performance data, curriculum goals and the community context (Illinois Professional Teaching Standards, 2011). It is important to follow such guides in planning, assessing and reporting so that appropriate evaluations are applied. These give more emphasis that teachers understand and use appropriate formative and summative assessments for determining students' need in everyday life like coming to school, monitoring students progress, measuring students growth and evaluating students' outcomes (Illinois Professional Teaching Standards, 2011).

School and society relationships means that the teacher knows the natural, socio-cultural and economic characteristics of the school environment (Ankara, 2006). Education is considered the most powerful instrument of social change. It is through education that the society can bring desirable changes and modernize itself (Mondal, 2015). Mondal (2015) added that the major function of education is the transmission of society's norms and values. Mondal (2015) maintains that society can survive only if there exists among its members a sufficient degree of homogeneity; education perpetuates and reinforces this homogeneity by inculcating in the child from the beginning the essential similarities which collective life demands.

School is a sub-system of the society. The two are so interrelated. The school performs certain functions for the society. It has been observed that the school must be based on the needs and demands of the society and that any school that fails to meet the needs and aspirations of the society is not relevant and is bound to fail (Daramola, 2013; Mondal, 2015). Conversely, it is known to all that the relation between school and society is very close and integral. One without the other does not carry any sense. These are two sides of the same coin. Schools are places which prepare the byproducts (learners) of the society (Mahmood, 2012). The interaction between the parents and teachers can bring about change in education. There should be a friendly environment between teachers and students so that students would not hesitate to ask questions (Khatoon et al., 2011).

Conversely, Quinton (2013) claimed that when students experience a sense of belonging at school and supportive relationships with teachers, parents, and classmates, they are motivated to participate actively and appropriately as well as create positive attitude in any learning activities in the classroom. This is supported by study of Schaps (2013), stating that student positive connections with their teachers and parents and when they feel that they (teachers and parents) care about them are what stimulate their effort and engagement. Also, positive school (teachers and students) and society (parents and other stakeholders) relationships create favorable attitude among students to take on academic challenges and work on social-emotional development (Gallagher, 2013).

Moreover, the teachers should not only confined themselves with neither the four walls of classroom nor corners of the school campus, but should also explore the community since the development of the learners include the community in general (Illustrisimo, 2007). Lastly, learners become a part of the community when we allow learning to be done in a richer learning environment like outside the room, beyond the school premises and using collaboration tools that allow learners to work with peers and other tools that are in use today (Boettcher, 2010).

Knowing the curriculum and content means that the teacher knows and implements fundamental values and principles that K to 12 is based on as well as approaches, targets, principles and techniques of the subject-specific curriculum (Ankara, 2006). Curriculum content is another main lever of education quality. The knowledge, skills and attitudes imparted by learning areas/subjects, cross-cutting approaches and extra-curricular activities is a main source of systematic and comprehensive learning. While learners may learn from many other different sources (especially in an informal way from the media and internet), curriculum's advantages in structuring and sequencing learning represent a major asset for sustainable acquisitions that ought to be capitalized on well exploited (UNESCO, 2014).

Differentiated curriculum is a way of thinking. It is a way of thinking about what our students really need to learn in school, how we teach students and how they learn; providing instruction that meets the needs, abilities and interests of our students (UNESCO, 2014). In addition, the author said that as teachers become more skilled they will be able to integrate additional components of curriculum differentiation. They will come to understand that curriculum differentiation is not "a variety of activities." It is a way of planning, assessing and teaching a heterogeneous group of students in one classroom where all students are learning at their optimal level.

In addition, quality of teachers and the abilities of teachers to teach content to diverse students that will carefully attend to the learning process and bring a positive result to the students in improving their attainment in school (Darling-Hammond & Bransford, 2008). In this challenging curriculum, student's achievement is determined by teacher's competency. In the same way, instruction is a specific method and activity by which a teacher influences learning (Alvarez & Espasa, 2009) while it was argued that instructions must be given in a wide range of methods which can be used by the diverse learners (Kirk, 2012).

Students' Attitude

Attitudes, in the conventional definition, are psychological tendencies that are expressed by evaluating a particular entity with some degree of (dis)favour (Albarracin, Johnson, Zanna, and Kumkale, 2005). In this definition, students are expected to manifest skills, knowledge and attitudes that will enhance their image as effective learners (Balance, 1990). Similarly stated, attitude becomes the element of positive participation in various activities (Zeng, Hipscher & Leung, 2010). Attitudes are borne from beliefs that shape a person's behavior (Rikard & Banville, 2010).

Another study stated that student's attitude is an integral part of learning and that it should become an essential component of pedagogy, for example, second language learning (Gajalakshmi, 2013). He added that attitudes toward learning are believed to influence behaviors, determined by individual beliefs about outcomes or attributes of performing the behavior (behavioral beliefs), and weighted by evaluations of those outcomes or attributes. Thus, a person who holds strong beliefs that positively valued outcomes will result from performing the behavior will have a positive attitude toward the behavior. Conversely, a person who thinks negatively will result to negative attitude towards behavior.

In addition, a study revealed that students attitudes are one of the major factors affecting learning (Shah, 2012), while students personality and style of interaction with their peers are reported to be very crucial variables in students' attitudes and achievement (Hsu, 2008). Students' general interest in technology may not be as easily affected as the more immediate attitudinal impacts of studying the consequences of technology or overcoming the difficulty of a technological problem (Boser & Daugherty, 2010).

Attitude towards technology is explicitly conceptualized not to contain a cognitive dimension. What a person knows about a – technological- subject can be correlated with his attitude towards that subject. Therefore, a person's attitude can provide a context for interpreting the results of an assessment on technological knowledge as an outcome variable for educational effectiveness (Ardies et al., 2013). Moreover, the authors added that technology impacts students' daily lives and certainly plays an important part in developing students' positive and negative attitudes toward it and translated into their adult lives.

Gender could also be an important predictor of attitudes towards technology. Female students consistently perceived technology to be less interesting than male students (de Klerk Wolters, 1989; Boser & Daugherty, 2010). Although all students' perceived technology as less difficult as they experienced technological learning activities, females believed technology to be a more difficult subject than did males.

As smart phones, tablets, social media, and other digital strategies reshape the way we educate our students and do our jobs, scientists and psychologists are beginning to question what our dependence on technology is doing to our minds (Elmore, 2012). Elmore (2012) added that there is a growing concern that technology is taking over our lives. Everyone knows that using technology has positive effects in teaching-learning process. However, inappropriate or overuse of technology has negative impact that can have serious and long-term consequences. Thus, to make the best out of technology, teachers and parents must also recognize their downsides and how to avoid them (DeLoatch, 2015). Students believed that technology was more difficult to work with at the beginning of the nine-week

program than at the end (Boser & Daugherty, 2010). Other studies on learning environment, showed that teachers are challenged to teach the students global issues and perspectives through more challenging instructions using the appropriate technological tools (Huffman & Huffman 2012; Paraskeva, Bouta & Papagianna, 2008; Teo, 2009). They added that students show positive attitude on technology in their class, students will accept that technology will be of great help to the instructions of teachers inside the class (Huffman & Huffman, 2012). The study propose that students who use appropriate technology will be more successful in the learning process (Huffman & Huffman 2012; Paraskeva et al., 2008; Teo, 2009).

Technological competence is one of the basis for engaging in learning activities. The analysis of technologies is a first step in describing and understanding the technology concepts (Schmoch, 2008). This concurred to the study of Kipperman (2009) which states that teaching technology concepts helps students organize their thinking about technology. By understanding these concepts and using them students will learn to see the broad patterns that are found across all technology fields. The dynamic nature of technology has contributed to the existence of various definitions and concepts of technology by the previous studies which are related to technology transfer. The discussion on the concept of technology is crucial in getting a clear understanding of the nature of technology and examining what the technology consists of (Wahab, Rose, & Osman, 2012). Therefore, learning the concepts of technology is necessary and should be required for all students (de Klerk Wolters, 1989; Jacobus, 2010).

Correlation between variables

Teaching competence and preparation enhance learning outcome, motivate students and develop students' attitude to learn (Siedentop, 1994). This is supported by Ericksen (1978) who pointed out that effective teaching in classroom depends on teacher's ability to maintain the interest and positive attitude that brought students to the course. This is further supported by Gajalakshmi (2013) who pointed out that if the teachers are competent and students have positive attitude towards any subject, they can achieve many things in that specific area.

Teachers who teach with enthusiasm will encourage or develop student motivation and attitude. Kheruniah (2013) stipulated that personality and competence of teachers have contributed enough to the success of education, especially in learning activities as well as in encouraging students to learn with enthusiasm. Another study found out that teaching competence has helped students' attitude to be more optimistic in different perspective and it has a significant effect to the students' lives (Burton, 2009). In like manner, a student can develop positive attitude towards learning because he learns to associate positive experiences or events with it as well as through teacher-related factors: teachers' enthusiasm, resourcefulness, helpful behavior and knowledge of the subject-matter (Mensah, Okyere & Kuranchie, 2013; Yara, 2009, Standslause, Maito, & Ochiel, 2013).

Moreover, Burton (2009) mentioned that teacher's different perspectives towards the students help the students develop a better attitude towards their subject. This is supported by Bibik and Smith (2010) that students who have positive attitude towards their chosen endeavor have greater chances of achieving the goals they have set through the nurture and help of their peers and teachers. The learner draws from his teacher's disposition and competence to form his own attitude (Kheruniah, 2013; Yara, 2009, Standslause et al., 2013) which may likely affect his learning outcomes. Thus, students' attitude and motivation to learn can be improved or aroused by teacher's skillful ability or competence. Similarly, Rink (2010) revealed that teaching competence in learning environment is as important to the development of a positive attitude of students.

A significant relationship was found between teacher competence and student attitude towards learning. This connotes that irrespective of the students' capability, if teachers display negative competence, students may not develop positive attitude towards the subject (Mensah et al., 2013). Likewise, teaching competence are employed to help learners accomplish their output and mark a record in order to show attitude, interest and participation to the class (Wolny, 2010). This proposition is supported by Zeng et al. (2010) that attitude becomes the element of a positive participation to the different perspective of teaching competence shown by the teachers. Teachers' competence and attitude toward teaching play a vital role in shaping the attitude of students toward learning the subject (Standslause et al., 2013). Mutahi (2008) confirmed that teachers' competence and attitude towards teaching affect their students' attitude to and achievement in the subject, while Balozi (2004) found significant causal relationship between the teacher's competence and attitude and students' achievement in any subject.

Moreover, Burton (2009) mentioned that teachers' different perspective towards the students helps the students develop a better attitude towards their subject. In the usual manner, teaching competence also means as the reflective teaching on experiences, attitudes, beliefs and teaching practices that will help students attitude towards learning (Bailey, 2010; Richards & Lockhart, 2004).

The above concept is in consonance with the idea of McLoughlin, Lee and Drexler (2010) that teaching competence is an avenue where learners create knowledge socially with attitude with the help of their peers and teacher. However, Tope (2012) emphasized that teaching competence is the single most important factor influencing students attainment thus teachers play an important role in the performance, attitudes, achievements of the students.

The above-mentioned review of related literature has relevance to the study undertaken by the researcher since they served as basis in the formulation of the objectives. Furthermore, the concepts collected from the readings guide the researcher in the development of the theoretical framework and in the discussion of the result of the study.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the non-experimental quantitative research design applying the correlational technique was used. This design is most commonly used when seeking statistical relationships between two variables without manipulating the data themselves (Alexander, 2012; Creswell, 2003).

The researcher used this non-experimental quantitative research design since the study determined the relationship between competence among Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers and students' attitude toward learning the subject.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Grade 10 students of selected secondary schools in Kidapawan City Division, school year 2016-2017. The Grade 10 students were chosen as the respondents of this study because they were the right persons to be evaluated since they have already done Grade 7, 8 and 9. Also, they belong to the second batch of K to 12 Enhanced Basic Education Program. To determine the number of samples, the probability random sampling procedure was employed and the Slovin Formula was used to determine the total samples of 320.

Instrument

There were two sets of questionnaire used in this study. One set was for the independent variable and another set for the dependent variable. The independent variable of this study is the competence among TLE teachers which is patterned after the work of Ankara (2006). On the other hand, the dependent variable is students' attitude toward learning the subject. This is based from study of Boser and Daugherty (2010).

The researcher modified the questionnaire to suit the study and to check the accurateness and appropriateness of the items in the questionnaires, the panel members were requested to validate the entire content of the questionnaire.

Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed and interpreted using the following statistical tools:

Mean. It measures the central tendency. This tool was used to provide the levels of competence among TLE teachers and students' attitude toward learning the subject.

Pearson r. It is the linear correlation between two variables. This statistical tool was used to determine the significant relationship between the competence among TLE teachers and students' attitude toward learning the subject.

Regression. It is the process of estimating the relationship among variables. This tool was used to determine which domain of competence among TLE teachers best predicts students' attitude toward learning the subject.

Results and Discussion

Level of Competence among TLE Teachers

Presented in Table 1 is the summary of the level of competence among TLE teachers. The standard deviation of 0.66 was less than 1.00 which indicated that responses of the respondents were fairly consistent. The overall mean score was 4.21 or very high which means that majority of the items regarding competence among TLE teachers were practiced at all times.

Table 1. *Level of Competence among TLE Teachers*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Personal and Professional Values	0.58	4.45	Very High
Knowing the Student	0.62	4.24	Very High
Learning and Teaching Process	0.59	4.33	Very High
Monitoring and Evaluation of Learning and Development	0.59	4.35	Very High
School and Society Relationships	0.93	3.47	High
Knowledge of Curriculum and Content	0.68	4.40	Very High
Overall	0.66	4.21	Very High

Taken individually, the indicators of the level of competence among TLE teachers of the participants were as follows: personal and professional values with a mean score of 4.45 or a descriptive equivalent of very high which means that the respondents claimed that the TLE teachers are skillful and competent in terms of their personal and professional values and have plans for personal and professional development to help students acquire more skills; knowledge of curriculum and content with a mean score of 4.40 or a descriptive equivalent of very high, which means that the respondents claimed that TLE teachers are knowledgeable of the content and manage teaching-learning process in accordance with the targets and principles of the Department of Education under K to 12 curriculum; monitoring and evaluation of learning and development with a mean score of 4.35 or a descriptive equivalent of very high,

which means that respondents claimed that their TLE teachers organize individual testing and assessment activities and use strategies to involve students in these activities; learning and teaching process with a mean score of 4.33 or a descriptive equivalent of very high which means that, TLE teachers prepare a student-centered lesson considering the individual differences of the learners and provide conducive learning environment so as to support learning; knowing the student with a mean score of 4.24 or a descriptive equivalent of very high, which means that respondents claimed that their TLE teachers know them well and consider their individual differences in planning teaching-learning process; and school and society relationships with a mean score of 3.47 or high which means that, respondents claimed that TLE teachers respect the different values and beliefs of families and enrich the teaching process by using materials unique to the environment.

Level of Student Attitude toward Learning the Subject

Shown in Table 2 is the summary of the level of student attitude towards learning the subject in selected public secondary schools in Kidapawan City, North Cotabato. The overall mean score was 3.58 or high which means that the Grade 10 students claimed that over all, they have high level attitude towards learning TLE subject.

Table 2. *Level of Student Attitude towards Learning the Subject*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
General Interest in Technology	0.57	4.06	High
Attitude Towards Technology	0.82	3.22	Moderate
Technology as Activity for Both Boys and Girls	0.90	3.17	Moderate
Consequences of Technology	0.64	4.35	Very High
Technology is Difficult	1.02	3.12	Moderate
Overall	0.79	3.58	High

In terms of its indicators, the level of student attitude towards learning the subject is as follows: consequences of technology acquired a highest mean score of 4.35 or very high, which means that, students claim that technology makes everything work better; general interest in technology follows with a mean score of 4.06 or high which means that students claim that they have an attitude of when something new is discovered; they want to know more about it immediately; attitude towards technology obtained a mean score of 3.22 or moderate which means that the students claimed that oftentimes technology needs a lot of mathematics; technology as an activity for boys and girls obtained a mean score of 3.17 or moderate which signified that the students claim their attitude towards learning TLE subject have often manifested as activity for both boys and girls; and technology is difficult garnered a mean score of 3.12 or moderate which signified students claim that sometimes to understand technology you have to take a difficult training course.

Significance of the Relationship between Competence among TLE Teachers and Student Attitude toward Learning the Subject

Table 3 discloses the results of the test of relationship between the variables considered in the study. The overall r-value of 0.233 with an overall p-value of 0.000 lower than 0.05 signified rejection of the null hypothesis showing that there is a significant relationship between competence among TLE teachers and student attitude toward learning the subject. This implies that their attitude towards learning the subject was positively correlated with the competence among Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers. It means that the more competent their TLE teachers, the better attitude they have toward learning the subject.

Table 3. *Significance of the Relationship between Competence among TLE Teachers and Student Attitude towards Learning the Subject*

<i>Competence among TLE Teachers</i>	<i>Student Attitude toward Learning the Subject</i>					<i>Overall</i>
	<i>General Interest in Technology</i>	<i>Attitude towards Technology</i>	<i>Technology as an Activity for Boys and Girls</i>	<i>Consequences of Technology</i>	<i>Technology is Difficult</i>	
Personal and Professional Values	.203** (.000)	.064 (.255)	.053 (.348)	.158** (.005)	.037 (.507)	.129* (.021)
Knowing the Student	.243** (.000)	.056 (.320)	.037 (.508)	.181** (.001)	.042 (.459)	.137* (.014)
Learning and Teaching Process	.238** (.000)	.046 (.417)	.054 (.333)	.235** (.000)	.025 (.651)	.144** (.010)
Monitoring and Evaluation of Learning and Development	.260** (.000)	.095 (.089)	.036 (.520)	.209** (.000)	.057 (.307)	.164** (.003)
School and Society Relationships	.214** (.000)	.269** (.000)	.216** (.000)	.093 (.097)	.230** (.000)	.302** (.000)
Knowledge of Curriculum and Content	.251** (.000)	.051 (.367)	-.010 (.862)	.184** (.001)	-.017 (.764)	.100 (.073)
Overall	.314** (.000)	.148** (.008)	.101 (.070)	.229** (.000)	.100 (.074)	.233** (.000)

Correspondingly, it is observed that personal and professional values competence among TLE teachers show significant relationship to general interest in technology with r-value of 0.231 and p-value of 0.000. It also shows positive relationship with consequences of technology with a computed r-value of 0.158 and p-value of 0.005. Result also shows that knowing the student has significant relationship with general interest in technology with r-value of 0.243 and p-value of 0.000 and it also shows significant relationship with consequences of technology with r-value of 0.181 and p-value of 0.001. Other indicators of competence among TLE teachers having significant relationship with general interest in technology are monitoring and evaluation of learning and development with r-value of 0.260, learning and teaching process with p-value of 0.238, and knowledge of the curriculum and content with r-value of 0.209 and with p-value lesser than 0.05 level of significance.

In addition, monitoring and evaluation of learning and development is significantly related to consequences of technology with r-value of 0.209 and p-value 0.000; learning and teaching process is significantly related to consequences of technology with r-value of 0.235 and p-value 0.000. Significant relationship is also found between knowledge of curriculum and content and consequences of technology with r-value of 0.184 and p-value of 0.001. Another computation revealed that school and society relationships is significantly related to general interest in technology having r-value of 0.214 and p-value of 0.000; related to attitude towards technology with r-value of 0.269 and p-value 0.000; related to technology as an activity for both boys and girls with r-value of 0.216 and p-value of 0.000; and related to technology is difficult with r-value of 0.230 and p-value 0.000 but does not show significant relationship with consequences of technology as indicated by its r-value of 0.093 and p-value greater than 0.05 level of significance.

On the contrary, personal and professional values does not show any significant relationship with attitude towards technology with r-value of 0.064 and p-value of 0.255, not related technology as an activity for boys and girls having r-value of 0.053 and p-value of 0.348, and not related with technology is difficult with r-value of 0.037 and p-value of 0.507. Other indicators of competence among TLE teachers which did not show any significant relationship with attitude towards technology, technology as an activity for both boys and girls, and technology is difficult are knowing the student with r-value of 0.56, 0.037, and 0.042 respectively with p-value greater than 0.05. In addition, learning and teaching process does not show significant relationship with attitude towards technology with r-value of 0.046 and p-value of 0.417, not related with technology as an activity for both boys and girls with r-value of 0.054 and p-value 0.333, and also not related with technology is difficult with r-value 0.025 and p-value of 0.651. Moreover, monitoring and evaluation of learning and development, and knowledge of curriculum and content did not show any significant relationship with attitude towards technology, technology as an activity for both boys and girls, technology is difficult as indicated by its computed r-value of 0.095, 0.036, 0.057 ; 0.051, -0.010 and -0.017 respectively and p-value greater than 0.05.

Significance of the Influence of Competence among TLE Teachers and Student Attitude toward Learning the Subject

Shown in Table 4 is the regression analysis of the competence among TLE teachers and students attitude towards learning the subject. The result of regression analysis clarified that school and society relationship has the highest degree of influence considering its 0.281 beta weight which can be inferred that school and society relationship was the best predictor of students’ attitude towards learning the subject.

The F- value of 5.778 is significant having a p- value of 0.000. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no best predictor of students’ attitude towards learning the subject was rejected. In addition, the R square of .100 signifies that 10 percent of the variation in students’ attitude towards learning the subject was explained by the competence among TLE teachers. This means that 90 percent of variation on students’ attitude is attributed to other variables not covered in this study.

Table 4. *Significance of the Influence of Competence among TLE Teachers on the Student Attitude toward Learning the Subject*

<i>Student Attitude toward Learning the Subject</i>				
<i>Competence among TLE Teachers (Indicators)</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Personal and Professional Values	.063	.066	.940	.348
Knowing the Student	.009	.010	.120	.904
Learning and Teaching Process	-.030	-.032	-.359	.720
Monitoring and Evaluation of Learning and Development	.085	.092	.955	.340
School and Society Relationships	.168	.281	4.862	.000
Knowledge of Curriculum and Content	-.044	-.055	-.680	.497
R	.316			
R ²	.100			
F	5.778			
P	.000			

Competence among TLE Teachers

The respondents’ overall level of teaching competence among TLE teachers is very high. This is derived from responses which registered both very high and high levels. Five indicators, namely, personal and professional values, knowing the student, learning and teaching process, monitoring and evaluation of learning and development, and knowledge of curriculum and content, registered very

high. Only one indicator, school and society relationships, had a rating of high.

The very high level result of personal and professional values strongly supported by the findings of Mizell (2010), Sawchuk (2010) and UNESCO (2014) who pointed out that effective professional development enables educators to develop their knowledge and improve their skills they need to address students' learning challenges and become a better teacher.

Likewise, this finding is a confirmation of the study of Marinkovic (2010) which claimed that professional development of teachers is a change of whole concept of the teaching profession and directly linked to a whole range of other aspects and certainly causes numerous other changes in the student attitude towards learning.

In the light of the above findings, it can be stressed that performance of teachers can be greatly improved or affected by their competence and this can be achieved through developing the personal and professional values of the teachers. The same assertion was made by Kamenarac (2011).

Another indicator of teacher competence with a very high level of response is knowing the student. This is strongly supported by the study of Ankara (2006) from which the survey instrument was adapted, they claimed that part of competence among teachers is knowing the students. The study of Ostwald-Kowald (2014) agreed that students gain strong benefits when their teachers recognize their strength and weaknesses as learners. Meanwhile, the findings of Powell and Powell (2011) revealed that the process of coming to know students as learners is often difficult and challenging, especially if the students are struggling with schoolwork.

The very high level of teaching and learning process indicates that overall the students claimed that in many instances teaching and learning process is true most of the time. The high level result is strongly supported by the study of Kheruniah (2013) which asserted that to create successful process of teaching and learning, a teacher must have ability and skill in teaching and realizing discipline to his students. This study is confirmed by study of Khatoun et al. (2011), which pointed out teaching and learning are important components of education. Therefore, a teacher needs to have his own philosophy of education to help his students and makes himself effective in teaching.

Another indicator of teacher competence which registered a descriptive equivalent of very high is monitoring and evaluation of learning and development. This finding is supported by Morin (2014) who claimed that self-monitoring is a skill used to keep track of your own actions and performance.

The last indicator of teacher competence which registered very high level result is knowledge of curriculum and content. It concurred with the finding UNESCO (2014), which stressed out that differentiated curriculum is a way of thinking. It is a way of thinking about what our students really need to learn in school, how we teach students and how they learn; providing instruction that meets the needs, abilities and interests of our students.

The only indicator of competence among TLE teachers which registered high level result is school and society relationships. Various studies have revealed the role of school and society relationships in bringing about social changes and academic achievement of the students. This idea was supported by the finding of Mondal (2015), who pointed out education (school) is considered the most powerful instrument of social change and students achievement. It is through education that society can bring desirable changes and modernize itself. The findings of Daramola (2013) and Mondal (2015) agreed that school is a sub-system of society. The two are interrelated. School performs certain functions for society. It has been observed that school must be based on the needs and demands of the society and that any school that fails to meet the needs and aspirations of the society, especially in developing students' attitude, is not relevant and is bound to fail.

One cannot think of a school without a society and a society without school is unimaginable. It is confirmed by the study of Mahmood (2012), which claimed that the relation between school and society is very close and integral. One without the other does not carry any sense. These are two sides of a same coin. Schools are places which prepare the byproducts (learners) of the society.

Student Attitude towards Learning the Subject

The level of student attitude towards learning the subject is high in descriptive equivalent. Among the five domains of the student attitude towards learning, only consequences of technology garnered a very high level result, while general interest in technology registered high descriptive equivalent. On the other hand, attitude towards technology, technology as activity for both boys and girls, and technology is difficult are described to be moderate. This indicates that the respondents claimed that overall, they have high level of attitude towards learning TLE subject in most cases.

The very high level of consequences of technology indicates that students claimed that in most cases technology has effect on their attitude and learning outcome. This is supported by study of Elmore (2012), which claimed that as smart phones, tablets, social media and other digital strategies reshape the way we educate our students and do our jobs, scientists and psychologists are beginning to question what our dependence on technology is doing to our minds. He added that there is a growing concern that technology is taking over our lives. Everyone knows that using technology has positive effects in teaching-learning process (Elmore, 2012). However, this is opposed by the study of DeLoatch (2015), which pointed out that inappropriate or overuse of technology has negative result that can have serious and long-term consequences. Thus, to make the best out of tools of technology, teachers and parents must also recognize

their downsides and how to avoid them.

The indicator general interest in technology registered a high descriptive equivalent. This implies that students claimed that they have an attitude of when something new is discovered, they want to know more about it immediately. It is supported by the finding of Boser and Daugherty (2010), which claimed that a student's general interest in technology may not be as easily affected as the more immediate attitudinal impacts of studying the consequences of technology or overcoming the difficulty of a technological problem.

Another indicator of student attitude which registered moderate level result is attitude towards technology. This implies that technology impacts student's daily lives and certainly plays an important part in developing students' positive and negative attitudes toward it and translated into their adult lives (Ardies, et al., 2013).

Technology as activity for both boys and girls is also moderate. The respondents claimed that TLE subject is often manifested as activity for both boys and girls. This result opposed the findings of de Klerk Wolters (1989) and Boser and Daugherty (2010), which pointed out that gender could be an important predictor of attitudes towards technology. Female students consistently perceived technology to be less interesting than did male students (De Klerk Wolters, 1989; Boser and Daugherty, 2010). They added, although all students' perceived technology as less difficult as they experienced technological learning activities, females believed technology to be a more difficult subject than did males.

Another indicator of student attitude towards learning which registered moderate level of result is technology is difficult. This implies that students claimed that technology is moderately difficult for them. This corresponded to the study of Boser and Daugherty (2010), which asserted that students believed that technology was more difficult to work with at the beginning of the nine-week program than at the end. The study of Schmoch (2008) suggested that to make technology easy one must develop his technological competence. This is the basis for engaging in any learning activities. He added, that the analysis of technologies is a first step in describing and understanding the technology concepts.

This is supported by the study of Kipperman (2009) which affirmed that teaching technology concepts helps students organize their thinking about technology. By understanding these concepts and using them, students will learn to see the broad patterns that are across all technology fields.

Significance of the Relationship between Competence among TLE Teachers and Student Attitude toward Learning the Subject

The test of relationship between variables reveals that there is a positive significant relationship between competence among technology and livelihood education teachers and student attitude towards learning the subject. This implies that the more competent teachers are, the better will be the student attitude towards learning.

There are various studies that support the result of this present study. Teachers who teach with enthusiasm will encourage or develop student motivation and attitude. Kheruniah (2013) stipulated that personality and competence of teachers have contributed enough to the success of education, especially in learning activities as well as in encouraging students to learn with enthusiasm. On the other hand, a student can develop positive attitude towards learning because he learns to associate positive experiences or events with it as well as through teacher-related factors: teachers' enthusiasm, resourcefulness, helpful behavior and knowledge of the subject-matter (Mensah et al., 2013; Yara, 2009).

This study confirms the findings of Khenuriah (2013) and Yara (2009) which claimed that the learner draws from his teacher's disposition and competence to form his own attitude, which may likely affect his learning outcomes. Thus, students' attitude and motivation to learn can be improved or aroused by teacher's skillful ability or competence.

Moreover, a study by Mensah et al. (2013) was conducted and disclosed that a significant relationship was found between teacher competence and student attitude towards learning. This connotes that irrespective of the students' capability if teachers display negative competence, students may not develop positive attitude towards the subject.

In the light of the aforementioned analyses, the result of this study validates the proposition of Siedentop (1994) from which this study was anchored, who pointed out that teaching competence and preparation enhance learning outcome and motivate students to learn. This also conformed to the proposition of Ericksen (1978) who pointed out that effective teaching in classroom depends on teacher's ability to maintain the interest and positive attitude that brought students to the course. Moreover, result of this study supported and agreed to proposition of Gajalakshmi (2013) who pointed out that if the teachers are competent and students have positive attitude towards any subject, they can achieve many things in that specific area.

Significance of the Influence of Competence among TLE Teachers in Relation to Student Attitude toward Learning the Subject

The regression analysis of the present study reveals that competence among technology and livelihood education was found to be a significant predictor of student attitude towards learning the subject. Among the six indicators of competence among TLE teachers, school and society relationships has the highest degree of influence considering its beta weight. This implies that school and society relationships is specifically the best predictor of student attitude towards learning.

This validates the study of Khatoon et al. (2011) done in Pakistan which disclosed that the interaction between the parents and teachers

can bring about change in education, particularly in students' attitude, learning outcome and achievement. This connotes that if the parents are supportive to the students' activities and undertakings in school, it boost the students' interest and attitude toward schooling and learning. In addition, this is in consonance with the study of Illustrisimo (2007) who pointed out that teachers should not only confused themselves with neither the four walls of classroom nor corners of the school campus, but should confine themselves to the community and the school but the development of the learners in general including the community. This finding is supported by Quinton (2013) who claimed that when students experience a sense of belonging at school and supportive relationships with teachers, parents, and classmates, they are motivated to participate actively and appropriately as well as create positive attitude in any learning activities in the classroom. This is further supported by study of Schaps (2013), stating that student positive connections with their teachers and parents and when they feel that they (teachers and parents) care about them are what stimulate their effort and engagement.

When teacher form friendly bonds with students, classroom become supportive spaces in which students can engage academically and socially. Gallagher (2013) positive school (teachers and students) and society (parents and other stakeholders) relationships create favorable attitude among students to take on academic challenges and work on social-emotional development.

In the light of the aforementioned analyses, the result of this study validates the proposition of Siedentop (1994) from which this study was anchored, which pointed out that teaching competence and preparation enhance learning outcome; motivate students; and develop students' attitude to learn. This also conformed to the proposition of Ericksen (1978) which pointed out that effective teaching in classroom depends on teacher's ability to maintain the interest and positive attitude that brought students to the course. Moreover, result of this study supported and agreed to proposition of Gajalakshmi (2013) which pointed out that if the teachers are competent and students have positive attitude towards any subject, they can achieve many things in that specific area.

Conclusions

The level of competence among technology and livelihood education teachers is very high. The level of student attitude towards learning is high as well. Competence among TLE teachers is significantly correlated with student attitude towards learning. Therefore, it implies that the more competent teachers are, the better will be the student attitude towards learning. Competence among TLE teachers positively influences student attitude. Among the six indicators of competence among TLE teachers, school and society relationships best predicts student attitude towards learning. Thus, this connotes that if the parents are supportive to the students' activities and undertakings in school and has positive relationship with teachers, it boost the students' interest and attitude toward schooling and learning. This is validated by the study of Khatoon et al. (2011), which disclosed that the interaction between the parents and teachers can bring about change in education, particularly in students' attitude, learning outcome and achievement.

Various studies confirmed the result of this present study. Kheruniah (2013) stipulated that personality and competence of teachers have contributed enough to the success of education, especially in learning activities as well as in encouraging students to learn with enthusiasm. On the other hand, a student can develop positive attitude towards learning because he learns to associate positive experiences or events with it as well as through teacher-related factors: teachers' enthusiasm, resourcefulness, helpful behavior and knowledge of the subject-matter (Mensah et al., 2013; Yara, 2009).

The findings of this study positively validate the propositions of Siedentop (1994); Ericksen (1978); and Gajalakshmi (2013) given that the respondents reported that their teachers are highly competent in maintaining their learning interest which motivate them and create positive attitude in them to perform well. Consequently, under competence among TLE teachers, the school and society relationships had significantly influence on student attitude towards learning.

References

- Albarracín, D., Johnson, B. T., Zanna, M. P., & Kumkale, G. T. (2005). Attitudes: Introduction and scope. *The handbook of attitudes*, 3-19.
- Alexander, C. M. (2012). Facebook usage and academic achievement of high school students: A quantitative analysis. Retrieved June 13, 2015 from <http://pqdtopen.proquest.com/doc/1112071638.html?FMT=AI>.
- Alvarez, I & Espasa, A. (2009). University teacher roles and competencies in online learning environment: A theoretical analysis of teaching learning. *European Journal of Teachers*, 32 (3), 321-336. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02619760802624104>
- Ardies, J., De Maeyer, S., & Gijbels, D. (2013). Reconstructing the pupils attitude towards technology-survey. *Design and Technology Education: An International Journal*, 18(1). Retrieved on July 14, 2015 from <http://ojs.lboro.ac.uk/ojs/index.php/DATE/article/view/1796/1730>
- Ankara (2006). Generic teacher competencies. Retrieved on April 17, 2014 from http://otmg.meb.gov.tr/belgeler/otmg/Generic_Teacher_Competencies.pdf
- Bailey, K. M., (2010) Competence and performance in language teaching. *Regional Language Center. Singapore RELC Journal*, 42, 227-264. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177%2F0033688210372953>
- Balance, M. (1990). *Administrators: Teachers and students attitude toward physical education*, North Carolina Central University, USA

- Balozi, C. (2004). Trends in teaching approaches and methods in science and mathematics education. SMASSE project
- Bhargava, A., and Pathy, M. K. (2014). Attitude of student teachers towards teaching profession. Retrieved on July 14, 2015 from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1043694>
- Bibik, J. & Smith, E. (2010). High school students attitudes towards physical education in Delaware: Journal on Physical Educator, 64 (4). Retrieved on November 15, 2016 from <https://ojs.lboro.ac.uk/DATE/article/view/1796>.
- Boettcher, M. E., (2010). Building sustainable community leadership capacity. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Boser, R. A., & Daugherty, M. K. (2010). Students' attitudes toward technology in selected technology education programs. Retrieved on April 24, 2015 from <http://scholar.lib.vt.edu/ejournals/JTE/v10n1/boser.html>
- Burton, R. (2009). Autonomy, competence & relatedness in the classroom: Applying self-determination theory to educational practice. SAGE Journals, 7(2) 133-144. DOI: 10.1177/1477878509104318
- Creswell, J. W. (2003). Research design. qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches. Second Edition. University of Nebraska, Lincoln SAGE Publications International Educational and Professional Publisher. Retrieved on May 15, 2015 from https://isites.harvard.edu/fs/docs/icb.topic1334586.files/2003_Creswell_A%20Framework%20for%20Design.pdf
- Crick, D. R. (2009). Pedagogy for citizenship in F. Oser & W. Veugelers (Eds.) getting involved: Global citizenship development and resources of moral values (31-55). Rotterdam: Sense Publishers.
- Daramola, C. O. (2013). Education and society: What type of relationship?. dr. sofoluwe, ao, 81. Retrieved on August 5, 2015 from http://www.unilorin.edu.ng/journals/education/nijef/march_2003/EDUCATION_AND_SOCIETY_WHAT_TYPE_OF_RELATIONSHIP.pdf.
- Darling-Hammond, L., & Bransford, M. (2008). Securing the right to learn: Policy and practice of powerful teaching and learning. Journal of Education, 189. DOI: 10.3102/0013189X035007013
- de Klerk Wolters, F. (1989). A PATT study among 10 to 12-year-old students in the Netherlands. Retrieved on August 15, 2015 from <http://scholar.lib.vt.edu/ejournals/JTE/v1n1/backup/falco.jte-v1n1.html>
- DeLoatch, P. (2015). The four negative sides of technology. Retrieved on August 5, 2015 from <http://www.edudemic.com/the-4-negative-side-effects-of-technology/>
- Demir, E., Desmet, P. M. A., Hekkert, P. (2009). Appraisal patterns of emotions in human-product interaction. Journal of Design, 3 (2), 120-125. UUID:a0d62534-4762-4178-99d6-c197b0aadca9
- Downes, S. (2010). The role of educator in PLE world. Retrieved on October 15, 2015 from <https://www.slideshare.net/Downes/the-role-of-the-educator-in-a-ple-world>
- Editorial Projects in Education Research Center. (2011). Issues A-Z: Professional development. Education Week. Retrieved August 6, 2015 from <http://www.edweek.org/ew/issues/professional-development/>
- Elmore, T. (2012). The unintended consequences of technology. Retrieved on August 5, 2015 from <http://growingleaders.com/blog/the-intended-consequences-of-technology/#sthash.T2eOQJKO.dpuf>
- Ericksen, S. C. (1978). The Lecture. Memo to the Faculty, no. 60. Ann Arbor: Center for Research on teaching and learning, University of Michigan, 3.
- Gajalakshmi, V. (2013). High school students' attitude toward learning english language. International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, 3(9), 1-7. Retrieved on August 4, 2015 from <http://www.ijsrp.org/research-paper-0913/ijsrp-p2152.pdf>
- Gallagher, E. (2013). The effects of teacher-student relationship: Social and academic outcomes of low-income middle and high school students. Retrieved on October 15, 2016 from <http://steinhardt.nyu.edu/appsych/opus/issues/2013/fall/gallagher>
- Gutteriez, N. (2012). The problem with philippine sport. Journal on Sports, 5. Retrieved on November 15, 2016 from <http://www.rappler.com/sports/10591-the-problem-with-philippine-sports>
- Hagger, H., & McIntyre, D. (2006). Learning teaching from teachers: Realizing the potential of school-based teacher education. Maidenhead Open University Press. Retrieved on November 15, 2016 from <https://www.amazon.co.uk/Learning-Teaching-Teachers-School-Based-Humanities/dp/0335202926>
- Hamilton-Ekeke, J. (2013). Conceptual framework of teachers' competence in relation to students' academic achievement. International Journal of Networks and Systems, 2(3), 15-20. Retrieved on June 15, 2015 from <http://warse.org/pdfs/2013/ijns01232013.pdf>
- Hsu, P. P. (2008). The relationship among teacher characteristics: Teacher-student interaction and students' academic achievement.

Bulletin of Educational Psychology. Retrieved on July 24, 2016 from <http://psycnet.apa.org/psycinfo/1985-18617-001>

Huffman, D., & Huffman, B. (2012). The intergenerational transmission of risk and trust attitude on technology. The review of economic studies. Restud, Oxford Journal of Research, 79 (2), 645-677. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdr027>

Huffman D., & Huffman, B. (2012) Building education & technology competencies for a changing society. Journal of Research, 50 (3), 1084-1091.

Illinois Professional Teaching Standards, (2011). State learning standards to advance social & emotional learning. SAGE Pub.com. Vol. 73(3) pp. 303-321.

Illustrisimo, R. D. (2007). Exploring links between perspective & academic motivation among Filipino. The psychology of asian learners. Pages 289-290. [Link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-576-1_18](http://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-576-1_18).

Jacobus, A. (2010). Attitude of university of zululand students towards technology. Retrieved on August 1, 2015 from <http://uzspace.uzulu.ac.za/handle/10530/610>

Kamenarac, O. D. (2011). Professional development: Personal construct of teachers. Andragoške studije, (2), 101-115. Retrieved on November 17, 2016 from <http://scindeks.ceon.rs/article.aspx?artid=0354-54151102101K>

Khatoon, H., Azeem, F., & Akhtar, S. H. (2011). The impact of different factors on teaching competencies at secondary level in Pakistan. Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, 3(5), 648-655. Retrieved on February 5, 2016 from [http://pakacademicsearch.com/pdf-files/edu/413/132-139%20Vol%204,%20No%203%20\(2013\).pdf](http://pakacademicsearch.com/pdf-files/edu/413/132-139%20Vol%204,%20No%203%20(2013).pdf)

Kheruniah, A. E. (2013). A teacher personality competence contribution to a student study motivation and discipline to fiqh lesson. International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research, 2(2), 108-112. Retrieved on February 5, 2016 from <http://www.ijstr.org/final-print/feb2013/A-Teacher-Personality-Competence-Contribution-To-A-Student-Study-Motivation-And-Discipline-To-Fiqh-Lesson.pdf>

Kipperman, D. (2009). Teaching through technology concepts. Strengthening the position of technology education in the curriculum. Retrieved on August 5, 2015 from [https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar?q=Kipperman,+D.+\(2009\).+Teaching+through+technology+concepts.+Strengthening+the+position+of+technology+education+in+the+curriculum.&hl=en&as_sdt=0&as_vis=1&oi=scholart&sa=X&ved=0CBoQgQMwAGoVChMI9eah3dKoxwIVRjGUCh128AMV](https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar?q=Kipperman,+D.+(2009).+Teaching+through+technology+concepts.+Strengthening+the+position+of+technology+education+in+the+curriculum.&hl=en&as_sdt=0&as_vis=1&oi=scholart&sa=X&ved=0CBoQgQMwAGoVChMI9eah3dKoxwIVRjGUCh128AMV)

Kirk, D. (2012). Physical education futures. London, Routledge. Retrieved on October 17, 2016 from <https://www.amazon.com/Physical-Education-Futures-David-Kirk/dp/041567736X>

Laguador, J. (2013a). Developing students attitude leading towards a life-changing career. Educational Research International, 1(3), 28-33. Retrieved on November 15, 2016 from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jake_Laguador/publication/311411776_DEVELOPING_STUDENTS'_ATTITUDE_LEADING_TOWARDS_A_LIFE-CHANGING_CAREER/links/5844dbeb08aeda6968191712.pdf

Laguador, J. (2014). Academic Performance and Measure of Character and Personality of Engineering Students With and Without Referral from Counselling Center. Asian Academic Research Journal of Social Science & Humanities, 1(16), 281-293. Retrieved on July 25, 2016 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311411613_ACADEMIC_PERFORMANCE_AND_MEASURE_OF_CHARACTER_AND_PERSONALITY_OF_ENGINEERING_STUDENTS_WITH_AND_WITHOUT_REFERRAL_FROM_COUNSELLING_CENT ER

Mahmood, A. (2012). The role of schools in building a peaceful society. Retrieved on August 2, 2015 from www.ipedr.com/vol30/25-ICEMI%202012-M00041.pdf

Marinković, S. (2010). Teacher's professional development and students' achievement. Retrieved on September 5, 2016 from <http://www.tepe2012.uni.lodz.pl/uploads/ThemenIV/Marinkovi%C4%87,%20Snezana;%20Bjeki%C4%87,%20Dragana%20&%20Zlati%C4%87,%20Lidija.pdf>

Marinković, S., Bjekić, D., & Zlatić, L. (2012). Teachers' competence as the indicator of the quality and condition of education. In Fourth Conference of Teacher Education Policy in Europe, Estonia. Retrieved on September 5, 2016 from <http://www.tepe2012.uni.lodz.pl/uploads/ThemenIV/Marinkovi%C4%87,%20Snezana;%20Bjeki%C4%87,%20Dragana%20&%20Zlati%C4%87,%20Lidija.pdf>

McLoughlin, C., Lee, M. J. W., & Drexler, W., (2010). Personalized & self-regulated learning in the web. 2.0 era: International exemplars' of innovative pedagogy using social software. Australasian Journal of Educational Technology, 26(1), 28-43. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.1100>

Mensah, J. K., Okyere, M., & Kuranchie, A. (2013). Student attitude towards mathematics and performance: Does the teacher attitude

matter. Journal of Education and Practice, 4(3), 132-139. Retrieved on February 5, 2016 from <http://tojde.anadolu.edu.tr/yonetim/icerik/makaleler/981-published.pdf>

Mizell, H. (2010). Why professional development matters. Learning forward. 504 South Locust Street, Oxford, OH 45056. Retrieved on August 6, 2015 from http://learningforward.org/docs/pdf/why_pd_matters_web.pdf?sfrsn=0

Mondal, P. (2015). The relationship between education and society. Retrieved on August 4, 2015 from <http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/education/the-relationship-between-education-and-society-7040-words/8584/>

Morgan, P. J. & Hansen, V. (2008). Classroom teacher's perceptions of the impact of barriers to teaching physical education on the quality of physical education program. Res QExerc Sport, 79, 506-516. DOI:10.1080/02701367.2008.10599517

Morin, A. (2014). 4 ways kids use self-monitoring to learn. Retrieved on December 12, 2015 from <https://www.understood.org/en/learning-attention-issues/child-learning-disabilities/executive-functioning-issues/4-ways-kids-use-self-monitoring-to-learn>

Mutahi, K. (2008). Increasing effectiveness of south-south cooperation: the Case of SMASSE Kenya and SMASE-WECSA. Retrieved on November 18, 2016 from [http://www.ajmse.leena-luna.co.jp/AJMSEPDFs/Vol.2\(3\)/AJMSE2013\(2.3-12\).pdf](http://www.ajmse.leena-luna.co.jp/AJMSEPDFs/Vol.2(3)/AJMSE2013(2.3-12).pdf)

Ostwald-Kowald, T. (2014). Understanding your students learning style: The theory of multiple intelligences. Retrieved on August 6, 2015 from <http://www.connectionsacademy.com/blog/posts/2013-01-18/Understanding-Your-Student-s-Learning-Style-The-Theory-of-Multiple-Intelligences.aspx>

Paraskeva, F., Bouta, H., & Papagianna, A. (2008). Individual characteristics and computer self-efficacy in secondary education teachers to integrate technology in educational practice. Computers & Education, 50(3), 1084-1091. DOI: 10.1016/j.compedu.2006.10.006

Powell, W. and Powell, O.K. (2011). How to teach now. Retrieved on August 6, 2015 from <http://jacandandy.blogspot.com/2015/05/how-to-teach-now-by-william-powell-and.html>

Quinton, S. (2013). Good teachers embrace their students' cultural backgrounds. Culturally relevant teaching. Retrieved on October 15, 2016 from <http://www.theatlantic.com/education/archive/2013/11/good-teachers-embrace-their-students-cultural-backgrounds/281337/>

Rana, P. S. (2013). A study of teaching competence in pre and post training of B.Ed. Trainees in relation to their rank difference in entrance test. EDUCATIONIA CONFAB, 46. Retrieved on August 21, 2016 from <http://www.confabjournals.com/confabjournals/images/63201395327.pdf>

Richards J. C., & Lockhart C. (2004). Competence and performance in language teaching. Regional language center. Singapore RELC Journal, 42, 227-264. DOI: 10.1177%2F0033688210372953

Rikard, G. L., & Banville, D. (2010). High school student attitudes about physical education. Education Society, 11, 385-400. DOI: 10.1080/13573320600924882

Rink, J. (2010). Teaching physical education for learning. 6th edition, McGraw-Hill, New York. Retrieved on August 25, 2016 from <https://www.amazon.com/Teaching-Physical-Education-Learning-Judith/dp/0073376523>

Sawchuk, S. (2010). Professional development for teachers at crossroads. Education Week, 30(11), s2-s4. Retrieved on August 24, 2016 from http://www.edweek.org/ew/articles/2010/11/10/11pd_overview.h30.html

Schmoch, U. (2008). Concept of a technology classification for country comparisons. Final report to the world intellectual property organisation (wipo), WIPO. Retrieved on October 5, 2016 from http://www.wipo.int/export/sites/www/ipstats/en/statistics/patents/pdf/wipo_ipc_technology.pdf

Schaps, E. (2013). The role of supportive school environments in promoting academic success. Sacramento, CA. Retrieved on August 15, 2016 from <https://www.collaborativeclassroom.org/research-articles-and-papers-the-role-of-supportive-school-environments-in-promoting-academic-success>

Shah, M. (2012). Comparative effectiveness of teacher training in enhancing the professional attitudes of b.ed. students. Institutes of Education and Research NWFP. College of Education Islamabad and Allama Iqbal Open University Islamabad. Ph.D. thesis Uni. A.I.O. Islamabad. p.232. Retrieved on June 17, 2016 from <http://www.aessweb.com/pdf-files/ijass-pp-1056-1066.pdf>

Siedentop, D. (1994). Sport education: Quality PE through positive sport experiences. Human Kinetics Publishers. Retrieved May 23, 2015 from https://books.google.com.ph/books/about/Sport_Education.html?id=hexyQgAACAAJ&redir_esc=y

Standlause, O. E., Maito, T. L., & Ochiel, J. O. (2013). Teachers and students attitude towards mathematics in secondary schools in Siaya county, Kenya. Asian Journal of Management Sciences and Education, 2, 116-123. Retrieved on September 12, 2016 from

[http://www.ajmse.leena-luna.co.jp/AJMSEPDFs/Vol.2\(3\)/AJMSE2013\(2.3-12\).pdf](http://www.ajmse.leena-luna.co.jp/AJMSEPDFs/Vol.2(3)/AJMSE2013(2.3-12).pdf)

Teo, T. (2009). Building education & technology competencies for a changing society. *Journal of Research*, 50 (3), 1084-1091. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10382046.2015.1106848>

Tope, O. (2012). Effects of teachers' competence on students' academic performance: A case study of Ikeja local government area of Lagos State. Ogun State, Nigeria. Retrieved on September 15, 2016 from <http://nigeria-education.org/content/effects-teachers%E2%80%99-competence-students%E2%80%99-academic-performance-case-study-ikeja-local>

UNESCO (2014). Changing teaching Practices. Retrieved on August 6, 2015 from <http://www.unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0013/001365/136583e.pdf>

Wahab, S. A., Rose, R. C., & Osman, S. I. W. (2012). Defining the concepts of technology and technology transfer: A literature analysis. *International Business Research*, 5(1), 61. Retrieved on August 5, 2015 from http://www.researchgate.net/publication/228450493_Defining_the_Concepts_of_Technology_and_Technology_Transfer_A_Literature_Analysis

Wolny, B. (2010). A physical education teacher as a part of school health education. *Human Movement*, 11(1), 81-88. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10038-010-0009-z>

Yara, P. O. (2009). Relationship between teachers' attitude and students' academic achievement in mathematics in some selected senior secondary schools in southwestern Nigeria. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 11(3), 364-369. DOI: 10.12973/eurasia.2017.00604a

Zeng, H. Z., Hipscher, M., & Leung, R. W. (2010). An examination in teaching behavior and learning activities in physical education class setting taught by three different levels of teachers. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 6, 18-28. DOI:10.3844/jssp.2010.18.28

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Raphy V. Abang, MAEd, MALT
Kidapawan City National High School
Department of Education – Philippines